

Digital Native Retail Investors’ Outlook towards Bespoke Digital Transformation in Mutual Fund Industry

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Meena, L. “Digital Native Retail Investors’ Outlook towards Bespoke Digital Transformation in Mutual Fund Industry.” *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 90–96.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567699>

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Abstract

Mutual fund industry is in the mesh of digitalisation, and has begun to use technology intelligently across all its processes - fund management, executing transactions, and customer servicing. In fact, digitalisation of the payments is the key to the industry’s rise in recent years. There are peak digital payment modes existing in India viz. Online / mobile wallets, Prepaid credit cards, Debit / RuPay cards, Aadhar Enabled Payment System (AEPS), Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) and United Payments Interface (UPI). This paper attempts to study the outlook of retail mutual fund investors in B30 city (Madurai) towards these digital payment modes. The study also intends to determine the investors’ perception in the direction of the digitalisation of mutual fund industry and its various processes. The key findings of the study indicate that retail investors hold positive approach / outlook towards Debit card payments, UPI and Prepaid credit card payments. The study recommended the Government and regulatory authorities to take efforts through investor education programmes to build confidence among the retail investors in B30 cities towards digital payment modes leading to a concrete way for balanced economic growth via exhaustive financial inclusion blurring the geographical divide.

Keywords: Digital payment mode, digitalisation, mutual fund and outlook.

Introduction

From the initiation of the digital era, accessing everything has become easier compared to the good old days of manual intervention. Digitization has touched upon various aspects of our lives. It all started with digitizing our social networks, purchase of goods online, transactions on the net, lifestyle enhancements and now our finances too.

A few years back, an investor living in a remote place could not have imagined having access to wealth advisory services. He might have invested in a savings bank account. Digitization has transformed this state of affairs. Organisations can now utilize their digital vigour to tap this customer community which was earlier under the radar and difficult to reach. Technology helps the mutual fund companies to cover a wider geographical reach, providing relevant and unbiased advisory and customer delight, all at the same time.

The government's role in digitization through vigorous financial inclusion - spreading financial awareness to the remotest parts of country and bridging geographical difference, is significant.

The financial markets are no exception. Mutual fund industry is in the mesh of digitalisation, and has begun to use technology intelligently across all its processes - fund management, executing transactions, and customer servicing. In fact, digitalisation of the payments is the key to the industry's rise in recent years. The industry's assets under management more than tripled from Rs 7.66 trillion in August 2013 to over Rs 25 trillion in August 2018.

Review of Literature

Bamasak carried out study in Saudi Arabia found that "there is a bright future for m-payment. Security of mobile payment transactions and the unauthorized use of mobile phones to make a payment were found to be of great concerns to the mobile phone users. Security and privacy were the major concerns for the consumers which affect the adoption of digital payment solutions. Doan illustrated the adoption of mobile wallet among consumers in Finland as only at the beginning stages of the Innovation-Decision Process".

A comprehensive model 'Payment Mode Influencing Consumer Purchase Model' was proposed by Braga and Mazzon. This model considered factors such as temporal orientation and separation, self-control and pain of payment constructs for digital wallet as a new payment mode. Consumer perspective of mobile payments and mobile payment technologies are two most important factors of mobile payments research. Mallat studied consumer adoption of mobile payments in Finland. Study found that mobile payment is dynamic and its adoption depends on lack of other payments methods and certain situational factors.

Following are some other advantages of making transactions through e wallets:

- Saves time
- Ease of use
- Security
- Convenient information saved under one roof
- Attractive discounts

"As per Ministry of Finance Report (December 2016) on Digital payment, financial inclusion is one of the foremost challenge facing India. 53 percent of India population had access to formal financial services. In this context, digital payment can act as accelerator to financial inclusion. Increasing availability of mobile phone, availability of data network infrastructure, rollout of 3G and 4G networks and large merchant eco system are the critical enablers of digital payment in India. It is further supported by the coordinated efforts of industry, regulator and government. As per RBI's report 'Vision 2018' four pronged strategy focusing on regulation, robust infrastructure, effective supervisory mechanism and customer centricity has been adopted to push adoption of digital payment in India."

Digital Payment Modes in India

Online or mobile wallets: They are used via the internet and through smartphone applications. Money can be stored on the app via recharge by debit or credit cards or net-banking.

Prepaid credit cards: Pre-loaded to individual's bank account. It is similar to a gift card; customers can make purchases using funds available on the card -and not on borrowed credit from the bank. Can be recharged like a mobile phone recharge, up to a prescribed limit.

Debit/RuPay cards: These are linked to an individual's bank account. These cards can be used at shops, ATMs, online wallets, micro-ATMs, and for e-commerce purchases. Debit cards have overtaken credit cards in India.

AEPS: The Aadhaar Enabled Payment System uses the 12-digit unique Aadhaar identification number to allow bank-to-bank transactions at PoS. AEPS services include balance enquiry, cash withdrawal, cash deposit, and Aadhaar to Aadhaar fund transfers.

USSD: Stands for Unstructured Supplementary Service Data based mobile banking. It is linked to merchant’s bank account and used via mobile phone on GSM network for payments up to Rs. 5,000 per day per customer.

UPI: The United Payments Interface (UPI) envisages being a system that powers multiple bank accounts onto a single mobile application platform (of any participating bank). Merges multiple banking features, ensures seamless fund routing, and merchant payments. It facilitates P2P fund transfers.

Statement of the Problem

In the past half-decade or so, the industry seems to have successfully bucked this trend, with the industry AUM galloping ahead at a fair clip – having more than doubled from 6.68 Lac crores to 13.39 Lac Crores between December 2011 and December 2015 (a healthy growth rate of close to 19 per cent per annum, compounded). Asides of the widespread efforts being undertaken by Asset Management Companies to educate the masses on the subtleties of Mutual Fund investing, possibly the single biggest driver of growth has been ‘technology as an enabler’ for the overall ecosystem.

Need for the Study

Research shows that the adoption of digital payments is higher in T30 cities (Top 30 cities in India based on the inflows of fund house) than in B30 peers (Beyond Top 30 cities). Also institutional investors use more digital payments compared to retail investors, as they have more knowledge of the financial avenues. With greater potential to be tapped in the remotest parts of the country, technology provides the much-needed push to expand the reach of the mutual fund products. Madurai is one among the emerging B30 cities in Tamilnadu with heterogeneous investors. It is the need of the hour to determine the retail investors’ outlook towards the digitalisation of mutual fund industry, which enables the industry to pave way to proceed in the path of transformation.

Objectives of the Study

The broader objective of the study is to know the attitude or outlook of retails investors’ towards bespoke digital transformation in the mutual fund industry. In order to achieve this objective, the study aims to achieve the following specific objectives:

- To determine the attitude of investors towards introduction of digitalisation in the complete process of mutual funds
- To identify the respondents’ approach towards the top five digital payment modes in India

Methodology

The study was descriptive in nature. The study was mainly based on primary data. The primary data has been gathered by means of interaction with various people and getting the questionnaires filled by them. Questionnaire was constructed in the way the objectives were clear to the respondents. The collected data was analysed carefully. The questionnaire was constructed with direct and structured questions. Questions of both open-ended and close-ended type were included. Open-ended questions were used only to draw qualitative suggestions from the respondents.

The method used for data collection was ‘Convenience sampling’, which is a type of non-probability sampling technique.

The Madurai (B30 city) was selected as the area of study and data was collected from 300 investors with the help of mutual fund distributors in the city during the period of March to August 2018, of which 80 were not interested to supply data and 20 respondents supplied contradictory responses. So the ultimate sample size was 200 for the study. The respondents were those who are mutual fund investors and have some knowledge about the basic terminologies involved with digital payments.

Tools and Techniques of Data Analysis

The statistical analysis carried out in the study was done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) software. The statistical tools used for analysis included: Weighted average with ranking, correlation and chi-square test as required by the broader objectives of the study. The data collected were analysed and interpreted in detail and were presented in charts and tables.

Results & Discussion

Based on the data collected from 200 retail mutual fund investors in Madurai, the appropriate statistical tools were applied and the important statistical analysis are summarised below:

Table 1 Age-wise Classification of Mutual fund investors

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage
18 – 30	24	12.0
30 – 45	104	52.0
45 – 60	57	28.5
Above 60	15	7.5
Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows age-wise classification of mutual fund investors in Madurai city. Out of total respondents, 52 percent were between the age group of 30 to 45 years, 28.5 percent were between 45 – 60 years, 12 percent between 18 – 30 years and only 7 percent were above 60 years.

Table 2 Annual Income-wise classification of mutual fund investors

Annual Income (in Rs.)	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 lakh	24	12.0
1 – 5 lakhs	152	76.0
5 – 10 lakhs	13	7.5
Above 10 lakhs	11	5.5
Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows annual income-wise classification of mutual fund investors. Out of total respondents, 76 percent fell in the income class of 1 to 5 lakhs p.a, 12 percent with less than one lakh, and 7.5 percent and 5.5 percent with 5 to lakhs and above 10 lakhs respectively.

Chart 1: Annual Income-wise classification of mutual fund investors

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 Mutual fund investors’ outlook towards Digital payment modes in India

Approach towards Digital payment modes	Strongly agree	Agree	Moderately agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Weighted Average	Rank
Online / Mobile wallet	25	57	20	18	80	35.27	4
Prepaid credit cards	10	40	45	84	21	35.6	3
Debit / RuPay cards	125	45	10	10	10	57.67	1
AEPS	20	32	8	28	112	28	5
USSD	8	7	10	10	165	18.87	6
UPI	124	45	8	15	8	57.47	2

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 shows the ranking of level of investors’ approach towards the positive statements about the digital payment modes by the mutual fund investors. As per the above table, it is evident that investors’ hold positive approach towards Debit card payments as it was ranked first, UPI was ranked second, prepaid credit cards and mobile wallets were ranked third and fourth, AEPS was ranked fifth and USSD was ranked last as sixth.

Investors’ Outlook towards Mobile Wallet Payments

In order to examine the formulated null hypothesis, chi-square test was employed. The computed results are given in Table 4.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their outlook towards mobile wallet payments

Table 4 Chi-square test between Demographic profile and investors’ outlook towards mobile wallet payments

Demographic factors	d.f	Chi-square value	P value	Inference (5% significance level)
Gender	4	6.668	0.155	Insignificant
Age	16	47.388	0.000	Significant
Marital status	12	48.073	0.000	Significant

Education	16	77.307	0.000	Significant
Employment status	20	100.942	0.000	Significant
Annual income	16	41.252	0.001	Significant

It could be inferred from the table 4 from above that other than gender, all the other demographic variables have significant relationship with investors' outlook towards mobile wallet payments for mutual fund investments.

Analysis of Variance (Anova)

ANOVA is conducted to understand whether the differences are significant with respect to the demographic variable gender with their outlook towards AEPS payments.

Hypothesis 2: The outlook of investors towards AEPS payments does not vary with gender

Table 5 One Way Anova Between Gender of the Respondents and Investors' Outlook Towards Aeps Payments

	Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
My outlook towards AEPS payments made for mutual fund investments is positive	Between groups	0.867	4	217	1.359	0.248
	Within groups	59.173	371	159		
	Total	60.040	375			

It is obvious from the table above that there is no significant difference (sig = 0.248) in outlook of respondents towards AEPS payments among different gender of the respondents at 5% level. This finding indicates that the approach among retail investors towards AEPS payments do not vary with their gender at 5%.

Recommendations

On the basis of the statistical interpretations and analysis, the following recommendations are put forth to the investment advisory firms, regulatory authorities & the government:

- Retail investors' hold poor approach towards USSD, AEPS and mobile wallet payment modes compared to other modes of digital payments. It is utmost need of the hour to gain investors' confidence towards these payment modes before enabling complete digitalisation of mutual fund industry. Confidence building programmes need to be conducted through well-educated distribution channel members who are in direct contact with investors. Such programmes make investors feel safe and secured and continue with their investments in the industry.
- Government initiatives on spreading financial awareness to the remotest parts of the country, the digital payments mode aspects must also be included. Exhaustive and effective financial inclusion is possible only when the geographical divide is blurred and proper awareness towards digital payments are created among the B30 cities also. This leads to the balanced economic growth and channelises investments towards productive avenues.
- Benefits of digital modes of payments and also digital processes must be made lucid to the retails investors in B30 cities. Their need to wade through mountains of paperwork to get started with their investments have vanished and this has to be put in plain words to them by the regulatory authorities at the time of investor education programmes.

Conclusion

Technology has now become a ubiquitous aspect of each and every element of Mutual Fund operations – be it transaction processing, fund management, customer service or distribution. This study is an attempt to understand the approach that retail investors in B30 cities hold towards the top digital payment modes that exist in India. The study has clearly brought out the mindset of investors towards the digitalisation of mutual fund industry.

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